

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭЛЕКТРОННЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГЕОГРАФИИ

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THE USE OF ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING GEOGRAPHY

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются применение информационных компьютерных технологий с использованием электронно образовательных ресурсов на уроках географии. Представлены опыт применения электронно образовательных ресурсов в учебном процессе. Выделены основные направления использования электронно образовательных ресурсов. Определены новые виды профессиональной деятельности учителя, связанные с применением информационных технологий при обучении географии.

Abstract

The article discusses the use of information computer technologies using electronic educational resources in geography lessons. The experience of using electronic educational resources in the educational process is presented. The main directions of using electronic educational resources are highlighted. New types of professional activity of teachers associated with the use of information technologies in teaching geography are identified.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии, электронные образовательные ресурсы, профессиональная деятельность учителя, компетентность.

Keywords: information technologies, electronic educational resources, teacher's professional activity, competence.

In the context of changes in all aspects of the life of our society, when its ideology, value system, and moral ideals change, the social role of the teacher increases and becomes more complex, and the requirements for his professional competence increase. Of particular importance are such qualities of the teacher as the ability to master new concepts of the discipline, new pedagogical technologies, as well as a broad approach to the content of the discipline and methods of its teaching.

The introduction of information technologies and the use of electronic educational resources in education significantly accelerates the transfer of knowledge and accumulated technological and social experience of humanity not only from generation to generation, but also from one person to another. Modern information technologies, improving the quality of education and professional training, allow a person to more successfully and quickly adapt to the environment and ongoing social changes. This will allow everyone to get the necessary education in today's and future post-industrial society. The active and effective introduction of these technologies in education is an important factor in creating an education system that meets the requirements of the process of reforming the traditional education system within the framework of the requirements of modern society [1].

In my teaching practice, I use many pedagogical technologies. Any lesson involves a combination of several technologies. At the moment, we call this process integration. Working on the issue of integrating the

educational sphere" technology " with other areas of education, I came to the conclusion that the main ones are design, information, integration, modeling. In the classroom, you can combine both pedagogical technologies and subject areas. The use of Information Computer Technologies with the use of electronic educational resources in geography lessons not only facilitates the assimilation of educational material, but also opens up new opportunities for the development of students 'creative abilities: increases students' motivation to learn; increases cognitive activity; develops thinking and creativity; forms an active life position. modern society [2].

In my teaching activity, I distinguish three main forms of working with electronic educational resources in geography lessons: first, direct use in the educational process. Secondly, the use of electronic educational resources to organize independent work of students on the subject of geography. Third, the use of electronic educational resources to provide cognitive leisure.

Computers and educational programs can be called universal learning tools. In teaching geography, I highlight the following areas of use of electronic educational resources: demonstration of educational materials; use in extracurricular activities; accumulation and systematization of students 'knowledge; independent work of students on the development of presentation projects; testing of students' knowledge.

Working with multimedia tools allows me to diversify the types of work in the classroom with the simultaneous use of illustrative, statistical, methodological, as well as audio and video materials.

Such work is carried out at various stages of the lesson: as a method of creating a problem situation, as a method of explaining new material, as a form of fixing what is read, as a form of checking homework, as a method of checking knowledge during the lesson. The combination of video, audio and text materials, comprehensive coverage of the topic provides a deeper immersion in the material, promotes its creative understanding, and increases motivation for learning. [3].

Here are some examples of using electronic educational resources:

1. Demonstration of training materials. The main visual aid has always been wall posters, maps, diagrams, educational films. With the help of multimedia tools, you can easily display materials from new Russian and foreign atlases, scientific publications on the internet. They allow you to focus on important objects and phenomena depicted on maps and other visual materials. The library of visual aids from geography includes visual materials of several categories: slides with photos of specific geographical objects with text comments (for example, photos of a ore sample, iceberg, volcano, etc.); slides with photos of phenomena with text comments on the results of a particular geographical process (for example, photos of cities destroyed after an earthquake); slides with drawings, diagrams, tables showing the structure of geographical objects, the essence of geographical phenomena and processes, their qualitative and quantitative characteristics (for example, a diagram of the structure of a volcano, a table describing Population Dynamics); videos showing geographical processes or phenomena with text comments (for example, waves); animation (for example, (for example, the formation of folded mountains); interactive maps and schematic maps with text comments.

2. Knowledge testing: the use of computer programs for automated control of students' knowledge (computer tests).

3. When organizing independent work of students: selection of necessary information; Study of lecture materials; implementation of practical work; preparation of abstracts, abstracts, research projects; preparation for competitions, olympiads; conducting research.

The use of information technologies in geography lessons allows me to implement individualization and differentiation of learning, increase the volume of work performed in the classroom, improve control over knowledge, rationally organize the educational process, develop research skills, and pay more attention to students' activities in the classroom. work independently, develop scientific thinking, and train at a high aesthetic and emotional level.

Over the past few years, the Department of geography and Natural Sciences of Zhetysu university named after I. Zhansugurov has been developing interactive electronic educational resources for subjects of

the Natural Science cycle, which allows you to use various types of independent work, as well as organize individual work with students.

The developed electronic resources include:

- * electronic textbooks for independent work of students;

- * educational and visual materials for lectures;

- * methodological developments for individual independent work;

- * interactive thematic modules containing materials on all types of curricula, including a laboratory workshop and test control of students' knowledge.

For the development of Students' Independence, teachers develop methodological recommendations for independent study of certain topics of the program material of the discipline, which contribute to: the formation of skills of independent assimilation of new educational material; the formation of skills of independent organization of mental work; the formation of professional competencies [4].

The creation of electronic educational resources included the following activities of teachers: search and selection of the content of the resource: theoretical information and materials for fixing and testing knowledge, the content of laboratory practice, homework and tasks for independent work; presentation of the material in electronic form; creation of a Bank of tasks for training and control testing; testing, correction of the content of the resource taking into account the identified shortcomings [5].

Practice shows that the use of presentation and Multimedia electronic resources, which are an interactive combination of text, graphics, sound, video and animation on a digital basis, significantly increases the visibility and accessibility of educational material. For example, in the lecture hall, when studying the topic "moisture circulation", the process of cloud formation in the discipline "Meteorology with the basics of climatology", students are invited to see an interactive virtual experiment confirming theoretical material that allows them to visualize the process under study.

The Department of geography and Natural Sciences has created a Bank of control and measurement materials in the form of tests to control students' knowledge of general and special disciplines, which is constantly updated. To perform interactive tasks, an electronic test Shell has been developed on the basis of the computer program Super Testing, which allows you to create a test with an unlimited number of questions using ready-made packages with tasks; you can devote time to solving the test; the program automatically evaluates them by entering them in the sign log.

Thus, from the point of view of modern requirements for the quality of student training, it is necessary to use in the educational process of the University, along with traditional teaching technologies, innovative technologies, including electronic educational resources that increase students' motivation to study the subject, as well as contribute to the formation of their professional competencies.

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ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫЕ МАСТЕРСКИЕ «LU BAN WORKSHOP», КАК ПРИМЕР УСПЕШНОГО ОПЫТА МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА КИТАЯ В РАМКАХ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНИЦИАТИВЫ «ОДИН ПОЯС – ОДИН ПУТЬ»

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PROFESSIONAL WORKSHOP "LU BAN " AS AN EXAMPLE OF CHINA'S SUCCESSFUL INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN THE NATIONAL BELT AND ROAD INITIATIVE

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Аннотация

Авторы статьи рассмотрели китайский бренд «Мастерская имени мастера Лю Бань», как новую меру содействия интернационализации профессионального образования. "Любанская мастерская" - это инновационный опыт объединяющий академическое образование и профессионально-техническое обучение. Этот проект берет на себя важную миссию по продвижению кооперации образовательных учреждений, способствующую как экономическому развитию, так и модернизации реформы профессионального образования, в рамках национальной инициативы «Один пояс – один путь». В статье авторы исследуют вопросы истории, коннотацию и принципы построения мастерской, выявляют текущую практику организации «Мастерской» с высшими образовательными учреждениями и профессиональными колледжами. Цель задачи и опыт организации мастерских «Luban Workshop», дают характеристику достижений этого бренда. Делают вывод, что китайский бренд «Luban Workshop» внес инновационный вклад в развитие глобальной профессиональной культуры и возможного продвижения бренда профессионального образования «Luban Workshop» в России.

Abstract

The authors of the article considered the Chinese brand "Master Liu Ban Workshop" as a new measure to promote the internationalization of vocational education. The Luban Workshop is an innovative experience that unites academic education and vocational training. This project takes on an important mission to promote the cooperation of educational institutions, contributing to both economic development and modernization of vocational education reform, as part of the national Belt and Road Initiative . In the article, the authors explore the issues of history, connotation and principles of building a workshop, identify the current practice of organizing the Workshop with higher educational institutions and professional colleges. The purpose of the task and the experience of organizing workshops "Luban Workshop" give a description of the achievements of this brand. It is concluded that the Chinese brand "Luban Workshop" made an innovative contribution to the development of global professional culture and the possible promotion of the brand of professional education "Luban Workshop" in Russia.